

Robustness and Coupled-System Feasibility Analysis of Variational Data Assimilation for Nuclear Reactor Parameter Calibration

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803964

ABSTRACT

Uncertainties in reactor numerical simulations necessitate the use of data assimilation (DA) to integrate measurement data and improve predictive reliability. Traditional filtering methods often diverge when addressing high-dimensional, multiphysics-coupled problems, limiting their applicability. This study systematically evaluates the performance and robustness of variational data assimilation (Var-DA) in complex engineering systems. Through a one-dimensional heat conduction problem, the analysis confirms the critical role of system observability in guiding assimilation performance. Results show that filtering methods perform better under ideal observation conditions; however, when observability is weak or sensor placement is suboptimal, filtering tends to diverge, whereas the variational approach remains stable, demonstrating its robustness in establishing physical correlations. The study further applies Var-DA to a two-dimensional pressurized water reactor multiphysics-coupled model for identifying the flow distribution flow area ratio parameter. The results indicate that assimilation accuracy is highly sensitive to observation error control but less sensitive to initial condition bias, effectively constraining large initial computational deviations. Moreover, fusing multi-source sensor data significantly improves assimilation performance, reducing the parameter relative error to as low as 2.92%. These findings confirm the feasibility and necessity of multi-source information fusion and demonstrate that Var-DA is compatible with complex multiphysics solvers, showing superior stability and reliability in strongly coupled nonlinear systems.

Keywords: Data Assimilation; Nuclear Reactor Parameter Identification; Observability Analysis; Multiphysics Coupling

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainties in nuclear reactor calculations arise from multiple sources. First, model parameters cannot always be accurately measured or tracked [1]. Second, simplifications and assumptions within the model introduce additional errors [2]. Third, inherent randomness in reactor operation, such as coolant flow patterns, fuel microstructural changes, and control rod positions, can further deviate from model predictions [3]. In addition, experimental measurements themselves are subject to errors. To reduce the overall uncertainty, it is necessary to integrate computational models with observed data [4], for which data assimilation (DA) provides an effective framework.

DA originated in numerical weather forecasting and was originally intended to address uncertainty in initial values[5]. Although its introduction to the nuclear energy sector was relatively recent, extensive research has demonstrated its feasibility. The simplicity of the filtering method has led to its widespread use in the estimation of neutronic parameters such as neutron flux[6], as well as fluid parameters like turbulence [7]. However, variational assimilation methods are still required for high-dimensional parameter estimation involving multi-physics coupling, such as in-core power distribution [8]. This is because these problems destroy the Gaussian assumption of filtering and cause filtering divergence[9]. Variational methods, particularly four-dimensional variational (4D-Var) methods, have been shown to

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be more robust and physically relevant, especially when dealing with model errors in coupled multi-physics problems[10]. However, variational assimilation relies on the system's tangent and adjoint modes, requiring customised computational software development. Currently, research in the nuclear energy field is limited. Case studies are needed to evaluate the performance of data assimilation schemes for complex physical fields based on variational assimilation.

In Section 2, we introduce the fundamental principles of variational data assimilation methods and the core concept of observability. In Section 3, the observability of a one-dimensional heat conduction problem with an internal heat source is firstly evaluated. These results are then compared with those of the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) method in a systematic analysis of the performance and stability of the 4D-Var method in this scenario. Furthermore, we extend our research to the more complex coupled steady-state neutronics and thermal-hydraulics problem of a two-dimensional pressurised water reactor. We explore the feasibility of combining variational methods with multiphysics coupling programs.

2. VARIATIONAL ASSIMILATION METHODS AND OBSERVABILITY ANALYSIS

This section first introduces the fundamental principles of 3D-Var and 4D-Var methods. Due to space constraints, the principles of the EKF method are detailed in the reference[11]. Next, we present the observability analysis principle introduced in this paper.

2.1. Variational Data Assimilation Method

2.1.1. Principle of three-dimensional variational method

The 3D-Var method is an optimisation-based static data assimilation technique. The fundamental principle underlying this methodology is the construction of a cost function, the purpose of which is to minimise the weighted sum of background field and observation field constraints. Here, "3D" generally refers to spatial correlation rather than temporal independence, making it suitable for simplified low-dimensional problems. The result of this process is optimal state estimates. The cost function is generally comprised of two weighted components, namely background error covariance and observation error covariance, which reflect model and observation-based uncertainties, respectively. The 3D-Var method performs assimilation only at a single point in time and is unable to directly handle time-series observation data. However, the implementation of this method is straightforward, and it is particularly well-suited for static state estimation in high-dimensional systems. The fundamental formula for 3D-Var is as follows:

$$J(x) = \frac{1}{2}(x - x_b)^T B^{-1}(x - x_b) + \frac{1}{2}(y - H(x))^T R^{-1}(y - H(x)). \quad (1)$$

In the equation above, x_b denotes the background (first-guess) state specified by prior information; B denotes the background error covariance matrix, which characterises the prior uncertainty of the physical variables; H denotes the observation operator, which defines the mapping from model state variables to observational space; and R denotes the observation error covariance matrix, which represents the uncertainty of instrumental measurements (and is typically calibratable). In this cost-function expression, the first term (involving B^{-1}) is commonly referred to as the background term, and the second term (involving R^{-1}) as the observation term.

Having defined the three-dimensional variational (3D-Var) cost function, the next objective is its minimisation. In practice, simple optimisation methods such as gradient descent or conjugate-gradient algorithms are often employed to quickly obtain the optimal estimate.

2.1.2. Principle of four-dimensional variational method

The 4D-Var method builds upon 3D-Var by extending the observation dimension to include time. It achieves optimal sequential estimation of state variables by integrating observations from multiple time points within a temporal window simultaneously. The incorporation of model dynamics constraints within the 4D-Var framework facilitates the integration of background errors, observation errors, and system evolution equations into the cost function. The model employs an adjoint model to compute

gradients, facilitating high-dimensional optimisation solutions. In comparison with 3D-Var, 4D-Var utilises the temporal evolution information of physical systems to a greater extent, thereby enhancing the estimation capabilities for unobserved variables and weakly observable parameters. However, this approach is associated with elevated computational costs, particularly in transient or strongly coupled multi-physics systems, thereby imposing augmented demands on the adjoint operator and iterative optimization. The fundamental formula for 4D-Var methods is as follows:

$$J(x_0) = \frac{1}{2}(x_0 - x_b)^T B^{-1}(x_0 - x_b) + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^K (y_k - H_k(x_k))^T R_k^{-1}(y_k - H_k(x_k)). \quad (2)$$

where x_k denotes the state variable at time step k , evolved through the physical operator. It has been demonstrated that 4D-Var methods are accompanied by a marked increase in computational complexity, which can be attributed to the presence of embedded physical operators, with a particular emphasis on multiphysics coupling operators. The forward gradient computation becomes particularly challenging when the optimization variables are high-dimensional. Consequently, 4D-Var methods typically employ backward gradient computation, achieved through tangential operators and adjoint operators.

2.2. Observability Evaluation Method

In systems with external excitation, observability serves as the theoretical foundation for evaluating the identifiability of system parameters. The term is employed to denote the capacity of a system to re-establish its internal state and parameters through the analysis of observed data. As one of the cornerstones of modern control theory, it constitutes the theoretical starting point for the identification of parameters and the design of observation systems. This paper introduces the parameter as an evaluation metric for assimilation systems. The dynamic system is assumed to be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k) \\ y_k = g(x_k, u_k) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Here, $x_k \in R^n$ denotes the system's state variables, $u_k \in R^m$ denotes the system's control variables (excitations or system input parameters), and y denotes the observations. In order to investigate the system's controllability and observability at the current operating point, the system is typically linearized around a reference trajectory point (x^*, u^*) . After linearization, the system is expressed in an increment form:

$$\begin{cases} \delta x_{k+1} = A\delta x_k + B\delta u_k \\ \delta y_k = C\delta x_k + D\delta u_k \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where A , B , C , and D denote the Jacobian matrices of nonlinear functions, defined as:

$$A = \frac{\partial f(x,u)}{\partial x} \Big|_{(x^*,u^*)}, B = \frac{\partial f(x,u)}{\partial u} \Big|_{(x^*,u^*)}, C = \frac{\partial g(x,u)}{\partial x} \Big|_{(x^*,u^*)}, D = \frac{\partial g(x,u)}{\partial u} \Big|_{(x^*,u^*)}. \quad (5)$$

We require that equation (5) uniquely determine δx . At this point, we define an observability matrix such that its rank is n :

$$\mathcal{O} = \begin{bmatrix} C \\ CA \\ \vdots \\ CA^{n-1} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

The derivation process of this matrix can be found in the reference[12]. If the system cannot achieve full rank, some parameters cannot be effectively observed. In this case, perform SVD decomposition on the \mathcal{O} matrix. The magnitude of singular values is indicative of the strength of observability. Therefore, the observability strength is defined as the numerical value of the corresponding component of the right singular vector in the normalized SVD decomposition. One of the objectives of this paper is to validate its relationship with the results of assimilation.

3. CASES STUDIED

In this section, all case studies treat numerical calculation results as true values and generate observed values by constructing artificial noise. This approach is consistent with the fundamental workflow of twin experiments in data assimilation, as outlined in the references provided[13].

3.1. Data Assimilation for a 1-D Heat Transfer Problem with an Internal Heat Source

This section compares the performance of the EKF and 4D-Var using a 1-D heat transfer problem with an internal heat source, while validating the guiding role of observability. The objective of this case is to estimate the intensity of the internal heat source and the initial temperature distribution. The problem is described as follows:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \alpha \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + q_0 \exp(-(x - x_0)^2 / \sigma^2). \quad (7)$$

Here, T denotes the temperature, α the thermal diffusivity, and the central intensity of the internal heat source q_0 is treated as an unknown quantity. In this problem, adiabatic boundary conditions are imposed, and the initial temperature is 293.15K. The parameter settings are provided in *Table I*.

Table I. Physical Parameters for 1-D Heat Transfer Problems.

Parameter Name	Value	Parameter Name	Value
Rod Length	10m	Heat Source Centre Position	5m
Thermal Diffusivity α	0.001 m ² /s	Heat Source Scale Parameter σ	0.1m
True Heat Source q_0	5.0K/s	Guessed Heat Source Strength q_b	3.0K/s

Table II presents the computational conditions for the benchmark cases. The indicated spatial and temporal resolutions correspond to the grid spacing and time-step size employed in the numerical calculations. The spatial and temporal resolution used in generating observational data remains constant, and observations are available at every time step of the numerical calculation. The origin of the observation points in the table is the center of the heat source. The table reports the relative error in the estimation of q_0 .

Table II. Benchmark cases of 1-D Heat Transfer Problems.

Case	1	2	3	4
Spatial resolution (m)	0.01	0.10	0.10	0.10
Temporal resolution (s)	0.01	0.01	1	5
Total number of observations	158	101	101	101
Observation point location (m)	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.50
Relative error of q_0 (%)	EKF	0.08	Not	0.50
	4D-Var	0.44	Converge	0.88
				Invalid

The benchmark cases above represent several typical scenarios. Case 1 verifies the assimilation performance under a well-designed system with high resolution. Cases 2-3 verify assimilation performance when the system design is suboptimal. Case 4 verifies system performance when sensors are located in non-sensitive regions.

Before presenting the results, it should be noted that since EKF is a sequential optimization algorithm, Figure 1 shows the error results for all time steps. In contrast, 4D-Var is a time window optimization algorithm, and the figure shows the results for a portion of the time windows, confirming that it fully reflects the relative trend.

As shown in Case 1, the EKF achieves better performance when the system is properly designed. *Figure 1(a)* illustrates the variation of the observability strength of q_0 over the observation time steps, indicating that the current configuration ensures a strongly observable state.

Figure 1. Results of the benchmark cases for 1-D heat transfer problem.

To assess the practical relevance of observability, three intermediate time points with insufficient observability were further examined as additional test cases. A rapid increase in observability corresponds to a significant reduction in estimation errors, confirming that state observability strongly affects data assimilation performance. In contrast, the 4D-Var yields lower errors under poor observability, demonstrating higher robustness. Case 2 reduces the spatial discretization accuracy of the numerical simulation. As shown in Figure 1(b), the observability strength of q_0 reaches only 0.4, indicating a weakly observable state. Under this condition, the assimilation system fails to converge, and temperature filtering divergence occurs. This is attributed to the excessively high temporal resolution, which prevents the assimilation system from effectively incorporating observational information. In Case 3, the temporal resolution is reduced to match the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) number of Case 1, after which observability recovers to a strong level, as shown in the figure. An additional test, Case 3-1, further decreases the temporal resolution to 5 s, leading to a faster improvement in observability. These results demonstrate that data assimilation remains feasible even under low-precision numerical computation conditions.

In Case 4, the sensor is placed 1.5 m away from the center of the heat source. Under this configuration, the filtering method fails to adjust q_0 , whereas the 4D-Var approach maintains stable information assimilation, as illustrated in Figure 1(c). Nevertheless, the performance of 4D-Var remains consistent with the system’s observability characteristics. This behavior arises from the distinct formulations of the Fisher Information Matrix (FIM) in the two methods. For the EKF, the FIM is given by:

$$\mathcal{F} = -E[\nabla_{\theta^2} \ln p(y | \theta)] = \frac{1}{S_k} \left(\frac{\partial x_k}{\partial \theta} \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{R}}(x_k(\theta)) \right)^T \left(\frac{\partial x_k}{\partial \theta} \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{R}}(x_k(\theta)) \right). \quad (8)$$

The above equation indicates that sensors must be placed in regions with strong sensitivity coefficients. Otherwise, it cannot effectively capture information. This highlights the EKF’s limited capability in establishing physical correlations and its strong dependence on local numerical sensitivity. For the 4D-Var approach, the FIM shows that its information content originates from the Hessian matrix of the cost function:

$$\mathcal{F} = E[\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta, x_0) \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta, x_0)^T] \approx \sum_{k=0}^N (\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{M}_{0,k}})^T R_k^{-1} (\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{R}, \mathcal{M}_{0,k}}). \quad (9)$$

This property enables 4D-Var to establish stronger physical correlations, allowing it to maintain satisfactory performance even under suboptimal sensor placement.

3.2. Data Assimilation Analysis of Multiphysics Coupling Problem in the Core of a 2-D Pressurized Water Reactor

The previous section discussed preparatory work before assimilation. Continuing from that, this section will discuss the assimilation effect of complex coupling problems, assuming observability testing is

passed. This case study employs a 2-D uniform pressurized water reactor (PWR) core as a multiphysics coupled model, solved using the Jacobian-free Newton Krylov (JFNK) method. The model adopts an r - z geometry with a height of 4 m and a radius of 1.5 m. Coolant enters from the bottom of the core at an inlet temperature of 290 °C and a velocity of 3.7 m/s, and exits from the top after heating. The steady-state total thermal power of the core is 4×10^9 W. Detailed modeling information can be found in the reference[14].

Based on this framework, an additional flow distribution channel is introduced to represent ineffective coolant flow. The flow distribution satisfies two constraints: equal pressure drop between the main and additional channels, and conservation of the total mass flow rate. The cross-sectional area of the distribution channel is treated as the assimilated parameter. As a steady-state case, the 3D-Var method is employed, and the model is designed to satisfy the observability requirements, making it a suitable benchmark problem for assimilation validation.

Table III. Benchmark cases of Multiphysics Coupling Problems.

Case	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
Measurement type	①Outlet temperature						②Pressure drop		①,②	
Background flow distribution area ratio	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	
Std. Dev. of observation noise	0.15	0.01	0.00	0.15	0.15	0.15	20	300	0.15,300	
Std. Dev. of matrix B	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	
Std. Dev. of matrix R	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.01	20	300	0.15,300	
Relative error of flow distribution ratio (%)	5.63	0.40	0.33	4.81	5.07	15.02	4.52	28.72	2.92	

Table III summarizes the benchmark case conditions. The observables in this problem include ① outlet temperature measurements and ② inlet–outlet pressure drop measurements. Ten temperature sensors are uniformly distributed within the radial range of 0–0.5 m in the core. The pressure measurement is assumed to provide the average differential pressure between the inlet and outlet.

The actual equivalent area ratio of the flow distribution channel to the main flow channel is 7%, while the initial estimate is 1%, indicating a substantial deviation. Cases 1–3 investigate the effect of observational noise by progressively reducing its magnitude. Although the prior observational error covariance R remains unchanged, lowering the actual observation noise has a pronounced impact on the assimilation results. Maintaining a low level of observation error significantly improves the accuracy of the assimilation.

In Case 4, the influence of initial parameter estimates on the assimilation results is examined. The results indicate that compared to observational noise, the variational results exhibit lower sensitivity to initial conditions, suggesting that variational assimilation possesses a degree of global convergence

Cases 5 and 6 investigate situations where the prior standard deviations in the background and observation error covariances (B and R) are underestimated. The results indicate that inaccuracies in the background error estimates have a relatively minor effect, whereas observational errors exert a more pronounced influence. These findings are favorable for data assimilation, as observational error levels can be reliably calibrated in advance.

In Cases 7 and 8, the main-flow pressure drop is used as the observation variable for parameter adjustment. The results show that, even under relatively low noise conditions, the pressure drop—being a single-point measurement—fails to effectively calibrate the parameters. To evaluate the effectiveness of multi-source sensor assimilation, the pressure drop data from the higher-noise scenario (Case 8) are combined with the temperature observations from Case 1. The results demonstrate that incorporating pressure drop information markedly reduces system errors compared with both baseline cases, confirming the feasibility and importance of multi-source sensor fusion in improving assimilation performance.

Figure 2 presents the assimilation performance at each observation point before and after assimilation, using Case 4 and Case 9 as representative examples. These two cases are illustrative: Case 4 exhibits a small initial estimation bias and accurately characterized observation errors, representing a typical data assimilation scenario. Case 9 involves multi-source sensor observations, demonstrating the feasibility and necessity of conducting assimilation using multi-field monitoring. The errors in the figure are

normalized by the standard deviation of observation noise, and the improvement is defined as the relative reduction in the deviation between observed and simulated values before and after assimilation:

$$I = \frac{|y^{\text{obs}} - y^{\text{b}}| - |y^{\text{obs}} - y^{\text{a}}|}{|y^{\text{obs}} - y^{\text{b}}|} \quad (10)$$

Figure 2. Multiphysics Coupling Case 4&9: assimilation status at each measurement point.

In Figure 2(a), the noise level at measurement point 4 deviates significantly from the initial estimate, leading to local temperature mismatches with observations and thus weaker improvement. Nevertheless, the final deviation between this point and the true value remains comparable to other measurement points, indicating that the assimilation may maintain physically coherent stability rather than mere curve fitting. Moreover, even when the initial computational error reaches as high as 6σ , the post-assimilation error can be effectively constrained to a very low level.

As shown in Figure 2(b), for observation points with large deviations from background values (points 1, 4, and 11), the assimilation results remain stable. Furthermore, under multi-physics coupled assimilation, joint monitoring of different physical quantities enables effective mutual correction, further reducing the overall field error. As summarized in Table III, incorporating even a single pressure measurement point allows multi-source sensor monitoring to achieve the lowest error level under identical observational noise conditions, strongly validating the necessity of performing assimilation based on multi-source monitoring.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This study demonstrates the feasibility and necessity of variational assimilation in engineering physical systems through 1-D heat conduction and 2-D pressurized water reactor (PWR) multiphysics coupling problems. The 1-D case confirms that system observability critically affects assimilation performance, highlighting the importance of observability analysis prior to assimilation. The variational method exhibits higher stability than filtering approaches in strongly coupled nonlinear problems. Its application to the reactor multiphysics coupling model further verifies its strong compatibility and robustness with complex solvers. Results show that assimilation accuracy is highly sensitive to observation error control, while variational assimilation exhibits global convergence characteristics. Moreover, multi-source sensor fusion significantly improves assimilation performance. Future research should emphasize pre-assimilation effectiveness analysis based on observability methods, refine sensor error modelling, and enhance multi-source observation fusion strategies to further improve the accuracy and reliability of nuclear system assimilation.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the LingChuang Research Project of China National Nuclear Corporation, National Natural Science Foundation of China 12275150, Beijing Natural Science Foundation number

1244054, Nuclear Technology R&D Program No. HNKF202307(60), and National KeyR&D Program of China number 2022YFB1903000.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Kong, Z. Gao, D. Wu, J. Cheng, and J. Wang, 'Geometric Uncertainty Analysis of Fuel Assembly Based on Sub-Channel Model', in *International Conference on Nuclear Engineering*, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2024, p. V010T12A001. Accessed: Oct. 20, 2025.
- [2] S. Zhang, L. Li, Z. Zhang, and S. Zhang, 'Three-dimensional modeling and loss-of-coolant accident analysis of high temperature gas cooled reactor', *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 150, p. 107840, 2021.
- [3] Y. Li *et al.*, 'Uncertainty Quantification of Engineering Parameters for a Nuclear Reactor Loaded with Dispersed Fuel Particles', *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 10, p. 2245, 2024.
- [4] D. G. Cacuci and R. Fang, 'Review of Fourth-Order Predictive Modeling and Illustrative Application to a Nuclear Reactor Benchmark. I. Typical High-Order Sensitivity and Uncertainty Analysis', *Energies*, vol. 17, no. 16, p. 3874, 2024.
- [5] G. Evensen, F. C. Vossepoel, and P. J. Van Leeuwen, *Data Assimilation Fundamentals: A Unified Formulation of the State and Parameter Estimation Problem*. in Springer Textbooks in Earth Sciences, Geography and Environment. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-96709-3.
- [6] W. Xiao, X. Liu, J. Zu, X. Chai, H. He, and T. Zhang, 'Operator inference driven data assimilation for high fidelity neutron transport', *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 430, p. 117214, 2024.
- [7] C. Intorini, S. Lorenzi, A. Cammi, D. Baroli, B. Peters, and S. Bordas, 'A Mass Conservative Kalman Filter Algorithm for Computational Thermo-Fluid Dynamics', *Materials*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 2222, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.3390/ma11112222.
- [8] S. Massart, S. Buis, P. Erhard, and G. Gacon, 'Use of 3D-VAR and Kalman Filter Approaches for Neutronic State and Parameter Estimation in Nuclear Reactors', *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, vol. 155, no. 3, pp. 409–424, Mar. 2007, doi: 10.13182/NSE07-A2673.
- [9] A. Spantini, R. Baptista, and Y. Marzouk, 'Coupling Techniques for Nonlinear Ensemble Filtering', *SIAM Rev.*, vol. 64, no. 4, pp. 921–953, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1137/20M1312204.
- [10] S. Skachko, Q. Errera, R. Ménard, Y. Christophe, and S. Chabrillat, 'Comparison of the ensemble Kalman filter and 4D-Var assimilation methods using a stratospheric tracer transport model', *Geoscientific Model Development*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1451–1465, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.5194/gmd-7-1451-2014.
- [11] P. S. Maybeck, *Stochastic models, estimation, and control*, vol. 3. Academic press, 1982. Accessed: Oct. 20, 2025. [Online].
- [12] R. E. Kalman, 'Mathematical Description of Linear Dynamical Systems', *Journal of the Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics Series A Control*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 152–192, Jan. 1963, doi: 10.1137/0301010.
- [13] L. Yu, K. Fennel, B. Wang, A. Laurent, K. R. Thompson, and L. K. Shay, 'Evaluation of nonidentical versus identical twin approaches for observation impact assessments: an ensemble-Kalman-filter-based ocean assimilation application for the Gulf of Mexico', *Ocean Science*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1801–1814, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.5194/os-15-1801-2019.
- [14] H. Zhang, J. Guo, J. Lu, J. Niu, F. Li, and Y. Xu, 'The comparison between nonlinear and linear preconditioning JFNK method for transient neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling problem', *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 132, pp. 357–368, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2019.04.053.